

Synthesis of alkoxyphthalimide derivatives of 5-arylidene-2-(6'-chlorobenzothiazol-2'-yl-imino)-4-thiazolidinones

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Synthesis and characterization of alkoxyphthalimide derivatives of 5-arylidene-2-(6'-chlorobenzothiazol-2'-yl-imino)-4-thiazolidinones are described. 2-Amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole **1** was converted to corresponding thioureas **2** by reacting with benzoyl thiocyanate and hydrolysing the product with sodium hydroxide. Compound **2** reacted with chloroacetic acid and anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanol to furnish corresponding thiazolidinone **3**. The reactive methylene group on the thiazolidinone ring was condensed with various substituted benzaldehydes to give 5-arylidene-2-(6'-chlorobenzothiazol-2'-yl-imino)-4-thiazolidinones **4** which on condensation with ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimides **5a-c** gave their alkoxyphthalimide derivatives **6** in good yields. All new compounds were characterized from ^1H NMR, IR, MS spectra and elemental analysis.

Thiazolidinones are important compounds due to their broad range of biological activities¹. We have reported here some compounds with amino-oxy moiety containing thiazolythiazolidinones.

Results and discussion

2-Amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole on reacting with benzoyl thiocyanate and hydrolysing the product with sodium hydroxide gave the corresponding thiocarbamide **2** in 68% yield. Cyclisation of **2** with chloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute alcohol furnished the corresponding thiazolidinone **3**. IR, mass and NMR studies confirmed the formation of **3**. The intense band at 1656 cm^{-1} for this showed C=N stretching for the phenylimino group attached to the thiazolidinone nucleus while the ring C=O group appeared at 1710 cm^{-1} . Compound **3** on condensation with *para*-substituted benzaldehydes in acetic acid in presence of sodium acetate gave **4a-c**. Formation of products was confirmed by disappearance of the IR band at 2939 cm^{-1} and NMR signal at δ 4.4 (singlet) for the CH_2 group of the thiazolidinone nucleus in **3** and appearance of new IR band at 1642 cm^{-1} and NMR signal at δ 6.4 (singlet) of C=CHAR in **4a**. ω -Bromoalkoxyphthalimides **5a-c** were prepared by reported methods. Condensation of **4a-c** with ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimides **5a-c** in absolute alcohol gave their alkoxyphthalimide derivatives **6a-c** in good yields. IR, mass and NMR spectra confirmed the condensation of **5a-c** with **4a-c** at the N atom. Free stretching vibration band for -NH group at $3300\text{--}3100$

cm^{-1} which was present in its precursors **4a-c** due to NHCO group, had disappeared and a strong band at $1300\text{--}1160\text{ cm}^{-1}$ appeared for the C-N stretching of the CH_2NCO group confirmed the formation of a new C-N bond. Furthermore, C=O stretching of the thiazolidinone ring was still present which confirmed the formation of the final compounds.

Antimicrobial activity :

The titled compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup or well method². Antibacterial activity of compounds have been evaluated against four bacterial strains viz. *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*. Sterilized nutrient agar medium was poured in Petri dishes and after solidification, these Petri dishes were inoculated with 0.2 ml suspension of organism employing spread plate method³. Two wells were made in each Petri plate and filled with two different concentrations viz. 500 ppm and 1000 ppm. The zones of inhibition were recorded after 24 h of incubation. Almost all compounds showed low to moderate activity against *K. pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa* and majority of the compounds were inactive against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* as compared to the standard drug (Ciprofloxacin) used.

Screening of the titled compounds for antifungal activity was carried out against two fungal strains viz. *A. fumigatus* and *C. albicans* using Fluconazole as a standard drug which showed that compounds **6a**, **6g** were highly ac-

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of compounds 6a to i

Compd.	Antibacterial activity (ppm)								Antifungal activity (ppm)			
	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>A. fumigatus</i>		<i>C. albicans</i>	
	500	1000	500	1000	500	1000	500	1000	500	1000	500	1000
6a	-	-	+	++	++	++	-	-	++	+++	++	+++
6b	-	-	+	+	+	++	-	-	+	++	+	++
6c	+	+	+	++	+	+	+	+	++	++	++	+++
6d	-	-	+	++	++	++	-	-	-	-	++	++
6e	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	++
6f	+	+	+	++	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	++
6g	++	++	+	+	+	+	+	+	++	+++	++	+++
6h	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	++	+	++
6i	+	++	+	+	+	++	+	+	++	++	++	++
Standard	+++	+++	++	++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++

Standard used : Antibacterial activity – Ciprofloxacin ; Antifungal activity – Fluconazole.

Zone of inhibition in mm, 3> = (no activity); 3–5 = + (mild activity); 5–10 = ++ (moderate activity); 10–15 = +++ (strong activity).

tive against *A. fumigatus* and other were good active while compounds 6d, 6e and 6f were not exhibited activity against *A. fumigatus* but they were found to be moderately active against *C. albicans*. So these thiazolidinones are found to exhibit good antifungal activity rather than antibacterial activity. Although in the present findings, the antibacterial and antifungal activity could not be directly related to the structure yet some conclusions have been drawn that increased antimicrobial activity was observed when arylidene unit was attached to the thiazolidinone nucleus but activity was found to be decreased when hydroxyl group was present at *p*-position in the arylidene unit and an increase in the number of carbon atoms in the alkoxyphthalimide moiety also increased the activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries. IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1800 and Shimadzu 8201 PC (4000–350 cm^{-1}) FTIR spectrophotometer. NMR spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were determined on Joel D-300 (EI) and Joel SX-102 (FAB) spectrometers. Purity of compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel-G plates and benzene-methanol or toluene-methanol as developing solvent and the spots were exposed in iodine chamber. Compounds 1 and 5a-c⁴ were prepared according to literature procedures.

N'-(6-Chlorobenzothiazol-2-yl) thiourea (2) :

A solution of ammonium thiocyanate (9 g) in acetone (50 ml) was taken inside a three necked flask provided with a reflux condenser, a dropping funnel and a mechanical stir-

rer. Benzoyl chloride (13 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. A solution of 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole (0.1 M) in acetone (50 ml) was added dropwise so that the solution was refluxed at its own temperature. The whole reaction mixture was poured into cold water (1 L) and the resulting precipitate was filtered off and hydrolysed by boiling with solution of NaOH (30 g) in water (300 ml). It was filtered and the filtrate was acidified with conc. HCl and made basic with ammonium hydroxide. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and crystallized from alcohol. Yield 65%, m.p. 220°C.

2-(6'-Chlorobenzothiazol-2'-yl-imino)-4-thiazolidinone (3) :

A mixture of *N*'-(6-chlorobenzothiazol-2-yl)thiourea (3.15 g), monochloroacetic acid (2 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) refluxed in ethanol (20 ml) for 6–7 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off under reduce pressure and the residue was treated with water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed several times with hot water, dried and crystallized from alcohol. Yield 70%, m.p. 200°C.

5-Benzylidene-2-(chlorobenzothiazol-2'-yl-imino)-4-thiazolidinone (4) :

A mixture of benzaldehyde (0.1 M), thiazolidinone 3 (0.1 M) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.2 M) was refluxed slowly in acetic acid for 4 h. After cooling, the solution was poured into ice-cold water and kept overnight. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water, dried and crystallized from alcohol. Yield 62%, m.p. 240°C.

3-(*N*-Ethoxyphthalimido)-5-benzylidene-2-(6'-chlorobenzothiazol-2'-yl-imino)-4-thiazolidinone (6a) :

A mixture of compound 4 (0.01 M), ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide (0.01 M), absolute alcohol (20 ml) and pyridine

x	n	x	n		
6a	H	2	6f	OCH ₃	3
b	OH	2	g	H	4
c	OCH ₃	2	h	OH	4
d	H	3	i	OCH ₃	4
e	OH	3			

(0.02 M) was refluxed for 13 h. Excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure. After cooling, the product separated was collected by filtration and recrystallized from absolute alcohol. Yield 60%, m.p. 260°C (Found : N, 9.96, $C_{27}H_{17}N_4O_5S_2Cl$ requires : N, 9.99%); ν_{max} 3028, 1650, 1710, 1680, 2890, 1385, 745, 685 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.6 (4H, m, ArH), 7.2–6.9 (8H, m, ArH), 6.3 (1H, s, C=CHAr), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.8 (2H, t, NCH₂); m/z 562 ($M^{+} + 2$), 560 (M^{+}), 370, 190, 132, 77, 76, 50.

Similarly other compounds were prepared.

6b (62%), m.p. 268°C (Found : N, 9.69, $C_{27}H_{17}N_4O_5S_2Cl$ requires : N, 9.71%); ν_{max} 3020, 1648, 1689, 1695, 2895, 1380, 740, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.7 (4H, m, ArH), 7.1–6.9 (7H, m, ArH), 5.4 (1H, br s, OH), 6.2 (1H, s, C=CHAr), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.8 (2H, t, NCH₂); m/z 578 ($M^{+} + 2$), 576 (M^{+}), 386, 190, 142, 50; **6c** (58%), m.p. 278°C (Found : N, 9.45, $C_{28}H_{19}N_4O_5S_2Cl$ requires : N, 9.48%); ν_{max} 3010, 1650, 1685, 1670, 2898, 1385, 750, 685 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.6 (4H, m, ArH), 7.2–6.9 (7H, m, ArH), 5.4 (1H, br s, OH), 6.2 (1H, s, C=CHAr), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.8 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.0 (2H, m, CH₂-CH₂-CH₂); m/z 592 ($M^{+} + 2$), 590 (M^{+}), 386, 201, 176, 132, 77, 76; **6f** (62%), m.p. 290°C (Found : N, 9.24, $C_{29}H_{21}N_4O_5S_2Cl$ requires : N, 9.26%); ν_{max} 3030, 2980, 1870, 1712, 1674, 1158, 682, 1382 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.7 (4H, m, ArH), 7.0–6.8 (7H, m, ArH), 3.5 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.3 (1H, s, C=CHAr), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.6 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.0 (2H, m, CH₂-CH₂-CH₂); m/z 606 ($M^{+} + 2$), 604 (M^{+}), 400, 204, 142, 104, 76, 50; **6h** (65%), m.p. >300°C (Found : N, 9.20, $C_{29}H_{21}N_4O_5S_2Cl$ requires : N, 9.26%); ν_{max} 3028, 2982, 2895, 1710, 1690, 1156, 675, 1380 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.5 (4H, m, ArH), 7.2–7.0 (7H, m, ArH), 6.1 (1H, br s, OH), 5.9 (1H, s, C=CHAr), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.7 (2H, t, NCH₂), 1.8 (2H, m, O-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-N), 1.6 (2H, m, N-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-O), m/z 606 ($M^{+} + 2$), 604 (M^{+}), 386, 218, 176, 142, 104, 77, 76; **6i** (62%), m.p. >300°C (Found : N, 9.20, $C_{29}H_{23}N_4O_5S_2Cl$ requires : N, 9.23%); ν_{max} 3030, 2980, 2890, 1700, 1670, 1384, 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.6 (4H, m, ArH), 7.0–6.7 (7H, m, ArH), 3.5 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.0 (1H, s, C=CHAr), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.6 (2H, t, NCH₂), 1.7 (2H, m, O-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-N), 1.5 (2H, m, N-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-O); m/z 608 ($M^{+} + 2$), 606 (M^{+}), 388, 218, 176, 132, 104, 77, 76, 50.

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